

RESKILLING

Deliverable D2.1

Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement Plan

Grant Agreement no.:	101147328
Project acronym:	RESKILLING
Project title:	Research initiative for Enhancing and Adapting Workforce SKILLS for Implementing TraNsport Automation with Employment Growth
Project coordinator name and organisation:	Matina Loukea, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH)

This project has received funding from the European Commission under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101147328

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Document Details	
Document identifier	Deliverable D2.1: Stakeholder mapping and engagement plan
Due Date of Delivery	30/06/2025
Actual Date of Delivery to EC	30/06/2025
Task Number	T2.1 - Stakeholder mapping, T2.2: Stakeholder engagement methodology & T2.3 - Stakeholder engagement and community report
Dissemination level	Public

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Control Sheet			
Version	Date	Editor	Summary
1	10/06/2025	Jorge Manso Garcia (POLIS, Belgium), Manon Coyne (POLIS, Belgium)	Table of Content & Intro
2	18/06/2025	Jorge Manso Garcia (POLIS, Belgium), Manon Coyne (POLIS, Belgium)	First complete draft
3	27/06/2025	Manon Coyne (POLIS)	Reviewed draft

List of Acronyms	
Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
D	Deliverable
ETT	Engagement Tracking Tool
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
M	Month
SC	Stakeholder Community
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable 2.1: Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement Plan provides a comprehensive identification of all relevant stakeholders to be engaged throughout the RESKILLING project. It outlines a strategic engagement plan, detailing the tools and methodologies developed and set up to ensure meaningful and sustained stakeholder involvement across all project phases. Additionally, the report addresses how these tools facilitate active participation, fostering collaboration and ensuring that stakeholder contributions are effectively integrated into the project's outcomes. After a first chapter introducing the purpose and intended audience of this deliverable, the second chapter describes the adopted approach to stakeholder engagement chosen in the RESKILLING project. Then, the third chapter presents the map of stakeholders identified and structured in categories, and the fourth chapter details the engagement activities and channels planned and developed. Following that, the fifth chapter provides a summary timeline of planned engagement, accompanied with a table defining specific timelines for each stakeholder category. Finally, the sixth chapter defines implementation and monitoring processes, and the last part before references and annexes lists all risks for the successful application of the plan.

This methodology will be subject to review and updates at key milestones (M18 and M28) to ensure that stakeholder engagement remains strategic, inclusive and responsive to the project's evolving goals and the needs of its target communities.

1. Introduction

The “Research initiative for Enhancing and Adapting Workforce SKILLS for Implementing TraNsport Automation with Employment Growth (RESKILLING)” project is a European Commission-funded initiative under Horizon Europe. It brings together 20 partners with the aim of responding to a key challenge currently faced by Europe's mobility sector: to ensure that workers and businesses are equipped to thrive in the context of disruptive technological change, especially with the deployment of Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions. In the context of the ongoing transformation of the mobility of people and goods due to automation and digitalisation, RESKILLING proposes a strategic, socially innovative approach to empower the sector's workforce, facilitate business model adaptation, and promote inclusive transitions that leave no one behind.

RESKILLING proposes the establishment of a comprehensive, multi-level framework to support territories and stakeholders in adapting to the socio-economic transformations associated with the CCAM deployment. The objective of the project is to propose, test and validate a set of novel tools and services that will enable workers, employers, authorities and intermediaries to navigate through and shape this shift. This includes analysing the impacts of CCAM across the entire value chain, designing pathways for skill development and redeployment, and fostering innovation ecosystems that can actively drive and co-create the future of mobility.

RESKILLING is built around a Co-Innovation Framework that centres inclusiveness, co-creation, and social innovation across all phases of the project to ensure that all results are contextually grounded, human-centred, and collaboratively shaped. Stakeholder engagement in RESKILLING is a foundational pillar determining the project's goals and processes. To that end, Work Package 2 is specifically dedicated to mapping, engaging, and mobilising a wide spectrum of stakeholders – from transport workers and industry representatives, to social partners, training providers, researchers, and public authorities - with the goal of creating and nurturing a dedicated Stakeholder Community. Stakeholders are expected to play a key role in shaping the project's outputs through co-creation activities, sharing expertise, validating tools, and ensuring that results are relevant and replicable across different modes in Europe.

This deliverable (D2.1) presents the Stakeholder Engagement Methodology that will guide this process. Building on the stakeholder mapping developed under Task 2.1, the methodology outlines the principles, processes, channels, and timeline for stakeholder engagement throughout the project. It defines both an overarching strategy and tailored approaches adapted to different stakeholder groups and project activities. It also establishes the foundations for creating and sustaining a RESKILLING Stakeholder Community that will continue to inform the project's direction and impact.

By aligning engagement activities with the project's Co-Innovation Framework and ensuring tight coordination with the different pillars and work packages on the project: effects on employment and socioeconomics effects (WP3), job creation, growth and innovation (WP4), impact assessment and roadmap (WP5), and dissemination, communication & exploitation activities (WP6), this methodology seeks to operationalise the project's ambition: to make CCAM transitions socially inclusive, territorially responsive, and anchored in real-world needs and expertise.

1.1. Purpose of the Document

This deliverable details the stakeholder engagement methodology that will guide the RESKILLING project across its 36 months duration. The primary objective of this document is to establish a

methodical, inclusive and adaptable strategy for engaging stakeholders who are either directly or indirectly involved in the social, economic and institutional transformations triggered by the implementation of CCAM solutions.

It outlines how stakeholders will be identified and categorised (based on their role within the CCAM value chain and the labour market) - using the results of the stakeholder mapping developed in Task 2.1, how engagement activities will be planned and implemented; and how their contributions will be integrated into the project's co-creation processes. The methodology provides both a strategic framework and practical guidance for project partners, ensuring that engagement is coordinated across tasks and aligned with RESKILLING's Co-Innovation Framework. The methodology defines how engagement will be organised across three interlinked phases:

- Scoping and Community Establishment;
- Co-Creation and Collaborative Design; and
- Reflection and Legacy.

It also provides the foundation for building and sustaining the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community (SC), a dynamic network of actors that will contribute to project activities including workshops, interviews, surveys, co-creation labs, and validation sessions. By doing so, it ensures transparency and accountability by clearly outlining when stakeholders will be engaged, through which activities, and for what purpose. It provides a shared reference for all partners and stakeholders, making the engagement process predictable, coordinated, and easy to follow across the project's lifecycle.

In addition, the document introduces the tools and mechanisms that will support this engagement, including the Engagement Tracking Tool (ETT) — which will monitor participation levels and KPIs across tasks — and a GDPR-compliant repository platform to collect, analyse and store stakeholder contributions (including reports, feedback, and recordings) that will be part of the Deliverable 2.3 - Stakeholder Engagement Report.

This methodology will be subject to review and updates at key milestones (M18 and M28) to ensure that stakeholder engagement remains strategic, inclusive and responsive to the project's evolving goals and the needs of its target communities.

1.2. Intended Audience

This deliverable is primarily intended for RESKILLING consortium partners who are responsible for designing, coordinating or implementing stakeholder-facing activities across the project. The document is intended to serve as a working reference for contributors to WP 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6, as mentioned in section 1.3.

It is also relevant for the project's Advisory Board, which plays a guiding role in ensuring that engagement activities remain inclusive, representative and aligned with ethical and scientific standards. This is also relevant for external evaluators and the European Commission services overseeing the project.

Beyond the consortium, the document is intended to be accessible to stakeholders. It clarifies the role expected for them in the project, the kind of input required, how their contributions will influence RESKILLING's direction and outputs, and how they will benefit from their collaboration. In addition, it

may serve as a useful reference for other project teams, researchers, and practitioners working on stakeholder engagement in the context of mobility innovation, labour transitions, or participatory governance. Drawing from established methodologies, EU project experience, and interdisciplinary academic literature, this document offers practical guidance to design inclusive, co-creative processes that link stakeholder input to research, policy, and decision-making.

1.3. Interrelations

This stakeholder engagement methodology is closely linked to several key components of the RESKILLING project. It builds directly on the stakeholder mapping, which provides the foundation for identifying and classifying stakeholders based on their position in the CCAM value chain, sector, and territorial context.

The methodology also supports and interacts with the implementation of engagement activities across multiple work packages.

- **WP3 – Short-, medium- and long-term employment and socio-economic effects of CCAM.** Stakeholders provide input through a variety of methods, including interviews, surveys and participatory scenario-building exercises.
- **WP4 – Towards job creation, growth and innovation.** The focus is on co-designing business model development and innovation toolkits, a mission-oriented approach to social, technological and training innovation, as well as training pathways.
- **WP5 – Impact Assessment & Roadmap.** This is the stage at which stakeholders are involved in testing and validating RESKILLING outputs in real-life settings.
- **WP6 – Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation.** Efforts to engage the public are aligned with activities to raise awareness and long-term outreach initiatives.

The methodology also informs **Task 2.3 and Deliverable 2.3 – Stakeholder Engagement and Community Report**, which will track participation levels, document engagement activities, and support continuous improvement of the strategy.

Lastly, the report ensures that all engagement activities across these work packages are consistent, coordinated, and based on shared principles. In addition, it contributes to the monitoring and reporting mechanisms of WP2 and WP6.

2. Engagement Approach and Principles

2.1. The Key role of Stakeholder Engagement

RESKILLING presents a framework designed to respond to the labour and skill transformations associated with the deployment of CCAM solutions based on inclusiveness, co-creation and social innovation. The project's scope extends beyond the development of tools or models for adapting to these transitions; it is founded on the principle of collaborative creation with those who will be directly affected.

In the context of RESKILLING, stakeholders are understood as individuals, groups, organisations or institutions that can affect, be affected by, or be involved in the development and implementation of CCAM-related strategies for employment, skills and workforce transformation, as well as those contributing to innovation and growth of mobility for people and goods. This includes those with direct operational or regulatory roles in the sector, as well as those whose interests and capacities are impacted by the outcomes of the project. It also understands the relationship of the different stakeholders to the topic and project as characterised by varying degrees of power, legitimacy, and urgency.

Therefore, the Co-Innovation Framework proposed by this project is a comprehensive approach that considers the various perspectives, needs, concerns and priorities of diverse stakeholder communities. This ensures a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities arising from CCAM. Through collaborative efforts and participatory processes, it empowers stakeholders to actively co-create innovative mechanisms and solutions that are both responsive and tailored to the specific contexts of the transportation/mobility ecosystem. It also facilitates the exploration of potential pathways for CCAM solutions and implementations to generate job creation and foster job growth through innovation.

In operational terms, stakeholder engagement is structured around a cyclical process, reflecting the principles of [stakeholder engagement for policy design and strategic foresight](#):

- **Exploration and scoping:** mapping stakeholders, understanding the labour and socio-economic impacts of CCAM, and identifying group-specific and territorial needs accordingly,
- **Co-creation and collaborative design:** working with stakeholders to jointly develop tools, training profiles, and skill development pathways that respond to their current and future realities, as well as ensuring growth and innovation in their sectors;
- **Reflection and legacy:** validating results and refining them through structured feedback loops, ensuring outputs are usable, replicable, and oriented toward long-term application (e.g. through policy recommendations and the RESKILLING Roadmap).

Figure 1 RESKILLING Stakeholder Engagement Graphic. Source: POLIS, 2025

To operationalise this, RESKILLING structures engagement across four levels, adapted from established stakeholder engagement models, such as the one from Durham et al. (2014) :

1. Inform – Ensuring stakeholders are aware of project objectives, activities, developments, and outcomes through accessible communication tools;
2. Consult – Gathering input from stakeholders to inform key decisions, especially where sectoral, local, or user-specific insights are needed;
3. Involve – Actively engaging stakeholders in shaping selected activities and outputs;
4. Collaborate – Co-developing solutions with stakeholders through structured processes such as co-creation labs, workshops, and interviews.

While all four levels are used at different points and for different stakeholder categories, RESKILLING places particular emphasis on consultation and collaboration. These modes allow the project to integrate stakeholder expertise into the heart of its design and delivery processes, ensuring that results are contextually grounded, socially relevant, and aligned with the wider transition to inclusive CCAM ecosystems.

Adopting this Co-Innovation Framework, the research project has two main aims. Firstly, it will comprehensively analyse the CCAM impact on employment and society. Secondly, it will proactively drive positive change by aligning technological advancements with societal needs and aspirations.

2.2. Theoretical Foundation

The centrality of stakeholder engagement in the RESKILLING project comes from contemporary research and policy guidance, which highlight that addressing systemic challenges requires collaborative, participatory approaches that go beyond traditional top-down policy design (OECD, 2022; European Commission, 2020; Kochskämper, 2017). Recent studies emphasize that stakeholder engagement is essential for capturing the diversity of expertise, values, and lived experiences necessary to co-create effective and context-sensitive solutions both for policy design and business management (Reed et al., 2018; Bryson et al., 2023). In particular, multi-actor engagement facilitates the identification of emerging needs, barriers, and opportunities across the transport ecosystem, enabling the project to anticipate implementation challenges and adapt interventions accordingly (Howlett, 2019; Oliviera et al., 2023; Hollebeek et al.2022).

According to contemporary theory, engagement is regarded as a form of governance. That is to say, it is a way to organise cooperation, align interests, and build shared responsibility across sectors (Kujala et al., 2022). In contexts where policy, technology and employment intersect, such as in CCAM, traditional top-down or expert-led approaches may not be sufficient to capture all institutional realities or local constraints. Stakeholder engagement provides an alternative approach by offering a collaborative space for problem definition, decision-making and foresight. In this way, affected actors are empowered to influence outcomes from within the process.

Furthermore, RESKILLING's stakeholder-driven approach is in line with a broader policy and research consensus that meaningful participation enhances the legitimacy, transparency, and long-term uptake of innovation. International institutions, such as the OECD and the European Commission have repeatedly emphasised that stakeholder engagement is vital for establishing trust, ensuring social acceptance, and enhancing the effectiveness of transformative projects, particularly in the context of technological and labour market changes (Bozzini, A & Pascual Dapena, 2025; European Commission, 2020; OECD, 2025; Reznikova et al., 2024).

This principle is explicitly embedded in the structure and mission of the CCAM Partnership, which calls for the active involvement of a wide spectrum of actors—including public authorities, transport operators, labour representatives, industry, research organisations, and civil society—as a prerequisite for steering CCAM deployment in a direction that is inclusive, context-sensitive, and societally beneficial. H2020 and Horizon Europe projects on CCAM such as [SHOW](#), [Drive2theFuture](#), [WE-Transform](#), [Diversify-CCAM](#), [FAME](#), [Move2CCAM](#), or [SINFONICA](#) provide practical precedents: they applied multi-level stakeholder engagement strategies to assess user needs, support business

model development, and address societal concerns, demonstrating the value of participatory processes in enhancing the relevance, the credibility, and the trust in technical and policy innovations.

2.3. Key Principles

The RESKILLING stakeholder engagement methodology is structured around three key principles: inclusiveness, co-creation and social innovation. These principles guide the design and implementation of engagement activities, ensuring that the process is technically robust, socially legitimate, representative, and impactful throughout the different phases.

Inclusiveness

Inclusiveness is understood as the outcome of deliberate efforts to integrate diversity into the design and implementation of engagement processes. Recognising diversity as a resource is integral to this process, as is ensuring that no group is systematically excluded from participation. Inclusiveness also refers to a community's capacity to involve all its members – particularly those who are often underrepresented in decision-making systems – in shaping policies, solutions, and governance arrangements.

In the context of RESKILLING, inclusiveness is not just about who is invited to participate, but how engagement is structured to reflect different perspectives, needs, and capacities. The project aims to involve a broad spectrum of stakeholders from across the CCAM value chain, including transport workers, SMEs, local authorities, education providers, and civil society. We are committed to ensuring that our outputs are not only comprehensive, but also contextually grounded and widely applicable. To this end, we pay close attention to territorial diversity, gender balance, and sectoral representation.

Co-creation

Co-creation in RESKILLING refers to the active involvement of diverse stakeholder groups in the co-design and development of knowledge, tools, and strategies. This includes collaborative participation in setting research priorities, shaping methodologies, gathering and interpreting data, and applying results to real-world settings. Rather than treating stakeholders as passive recipients of project outputs, the co-creation principle positions them as contributors and collaborators. This helps to balance interests, distribute responsibilities, and make processes more transparent, needs-driven, and accountable. In practice, co-creation is embedded in the other pillars such as Jobs, Skills & Education (II), Growth & (Social) Innovation (III) through different types of activities such as interviews, surveys, workshops, and living labs — all structured to support mutual learning and ensure that project's outputs reflect real stakeholder needs and institutional contexts.

Social Innovation

Social Innovation can be defined as the development and implementation of new solutions to social problems that are more effective, inclusive, or sustainable than existing alternatives. It is important to note that the value created by these solutions is primarily shared with society as a whole, rather than with individual market participants (Phillips et al., 2015).

RESKILLING's stakeholder engagement methodology is structured as a social innovation process in itself. The objective of the project is twofold: firstly, to inform about project results, and secondly, to reshape how institutions and actors collaborate around future labour challenges.

3. Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping process aims to provide a strategic foundation for the project's engagement activities. Its main objective is to identify, categorise and assess the actors involved in, affected by, or capable of influencing the transformation of jobs and skills, as well as business models in the context of CCAM. This includes both the workforce directly engaged in transport and mobility systems, and the broader institutional and educational ecosystems that shapes employment, training, governance, and innovation.

The mapping serves three key purposes:

1. To support the creation of a dynamic and inclusive Stakeholder Community on jobs and skills in the transport sector, enabling long-term collaboration and learning beyond the duration of the project;
2. To structure and harmonise outreach across relevant stakeholder groups, ensuring their meaningful and timely involvement in co-creation, validation, and dissemination activities;
3. To position RESKILLING within the broader European CCAM ecosystem, by aligning with ongoing efforts in CCAM-related partnerships, strategic research agendas, and concertation initiatives.

The stakeholder mapping also informs the operationalisation of the RESKILLING Co-Innovation Framework. It ensures that engagement efforts across the project are targeted, inclusive, and adapted to the diversity of professional roles, organisational types, territorial contexts, and institutional responsibilities involved in CCAM deployment.

The following subsections present the classification of stakeholder categories (3.1), their relevance and expected benefits (3.2), and the method used to structure the mapping (3.3).

Stakeholders will interact with the project in differentiated but coordinated ways. While some will be involved across multiple WPs as part of the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community — including in interviews, co-creation workshops, surveys or validation activities — others will contribute at specific stages, such as the co-design of training content, the validation of tools, or the testing of inclusive communication strategies. The engagement approach combines an overarching framework with targeted methods for each stakeholder group, avoiding redundancy and ensuring proportional involvement. Activities will be supported by both digital and in-person tools, including an annual online stakeholder engagement event, a dedicated Stakeholder Forum in the form of an online platform linked on the project website, and a GDPR-compliant repository for contributions. This structured categorisation ensures that stakeholder voices are not only heard, but strategically integrated into the design and implementation of fair, inclusive and future-ready CCAM employment and training policies.

3.1. Stakeholder Categories

To structure meaningful engagement and reflect the full complexity of the CCAM transition, the consortium defines a set of stakeholder categories that go beyond traditional CCAM classifications. The categorisation developed under Task 2.1 identifies seven main stakeholder categories, each further divided into specific sub-categories and stakeholder granular types. These categories aim to capture the diversity of actors who influence or are influenced by the transition of CCAM and their

employment and skills implications — including those who design, regulate, deliver, use, and are impacted by mobility services.

The classification spans public authorities at all levels, transport and technology providers, infrastructure managers, industrial and service-sector employers, workers and unions, training and education institutions, end-users and civil society, as well as funders and insurers. Importantly, the mapping also includes groups often marginalised in innovation processes, such as the unemployed, informal workers, and vulnerable users. This structured taxonomy serves both as an analytical tool to understand roles and relationships in the evolving CCAM ecosystem, and as a practical framework to guide engagement efforts across the project’s lifetime. It ensures that stakeholder input can be collected and integrated in a coherent and inclusive way, tailored to the specific contributions and perspectives of each group.

These categories are not static labels, but guide how stakeholders will interact with the project. Some will co-develop training content, others will test tools, advise on governance strategies, or bring in the voice of underrepresented groups.

Figure 2. Map of Stakeholder Categories and sub-categories

RESKILLING STAKEHOLDERS		
Stakeholder Main Categories	Stakeholder Sub-Categories	Stakeholder Profiles
Transport operators	Service Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fleet operators Fleet owners Passenger transport service providers Logistic service providers Car-sharing platform operators On-demand transport operators Military service providers
	Technology Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital innovators/ developers ITS associations MaaS Providers Telecom operators
	Infrastructure operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roads/Railways owners Roads/Railways operators Port/Airport/Train & Coach station/Parking operators
Industry	Transport industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle manufacturers (Pre-delivery inspection & storage parking lots, Vehicle designers, Factories) Vehicle components manufacturers Signalling manufacturers Repair & maintenance operators (Workshops, Repair centres, Bodyshops, Assistance & tow trucks, Fast fitters)
	Telecom industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Device manufacturers Device maintenance Equipment providers Infrastructure installers Infrastructure maintenance
	Recycling & waste management industry	
	Buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real Estate Architects Construction companies
	Energy industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy providers Grid owners Local distributors
Workers	People working	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operational workers (Industry workers, Service workers, Other operational workers) Instructors Planners Service Intermediaries Innovation workers
	Unions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unions' associations National unions Local unions
	Human resources responsables	
	Unemployed people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential workers

Stakeholder Main Categories	Stakeholder Sub-Categories	Stakeholder Profiles
Authorities	International Authorities	
	European Authorities	
	National Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport Ministry • Labour Ministry • Economic development & innovation ministry • Defense Ministry
	Regional & Local Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City planner • Transport planner
	Employment Agencies	
	Enforcement authorities	
	Standard definition agencies	
Funders & Insurers	Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private funders • Public funders
	Insurers	
Researchers & Educators	Universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students • Professors • Programme direction
	Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economists • Social scientists • Transport innovators • Environment researchers
	Vocational /technical training	
	Life-long learning organisations	
	Private research centers	
	Innovation clusters	
End users	Transport / Infrastructure users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Car drivers • Cyclists • Pedestrians • Passengers
	Tourist operators	
	Event organisers	
	Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual consumers (e-buyers, car drivers...) • Business consumers (logistics buyers) • Services of general Interest
	Organised Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific user groups • Minority representation • Neighbourhood management • Associations • Advocacy groups

3.2. Stakeholders' Relevance and Benefits

As a pillar of the project, stakeholder participation is a central part of how the project creates knowledge, ensures relevance, and delivers impact. Stakeholders are essential contributors to understanding how the deployment of CCAM affects employment, training, and institutional dynamics across Europe. Their insights, needs, and decisions shape how the mobility sector will adapt — and how the transition can be made just, inclusive, and future-ready.

Stakeholders' relevance lies in the expertise, institutional role, or operational knowledge they contribute to:

- Identifying sector- and group-specific skills needs and employment risks;
- Informing the design of re-training modules, business models, and innovation pathways;
- Shaping policy recommendations and transferability strategies that match local or industry contexts;
- Supporting data collection and co-validation of findings through lived experience.

In return, stakeholders benefit from being directly involved in a project that:

- Offers early access to insights and tools emerging from applied research, including the CCAM Employment & Skills Observatory — a knowledge hub that will centralise use cases, training pathways, and employment trends, tailored to stakeholder needs;
- Provides visibility and influence within a structured and recognised process, including participation in co-creation workshops, targeted interviews, and public-facing events;
- Connects them to a multi-sectoral European network through the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community, enabling exchanges with peers, cities, researchers, businesses, and civil society actors;
- Supports their strategic adaptation by offering tailored knowledge, updates on key labour-related developments in CCAM, and the opportunity to contribute to tools that will inform future investment, training, and employment policies.

This section outlines how each stakeholder category contributes to the RESKILLING project and what they stand to gain through participation.

Stakeholder Sub-Category	Relevance for the Project	Benefits for Stakeholders
Service Providers	Provide real-world use cases, user feedback, and infrastructure access for deployment and piloting of tools.	Gain early access to tools and strategies that enhance operational models and service delivery.
Technology Providers	Enable the technological integration and application of RESKILLING tools through innovation and product alignment.	Align product offerings with cutting-edge CCAM workforce and policy strategies.
Infrastructure operators	Support the adaptation and testing of infrastructure to meet new mobility demands, aligning with CCAM development.	Shape the adaptation of infrastructure to emerging technological and social demands.
Transport industry	Deliver market trends and labour dynamics critical for developing responsive skills strategies.	Anticipate future workforce trends and prepare for emerging skill demands and policy shifts.
Telecom industry	Provide connectivity frameworks and insights essential for supporting data-driven CCAM solutions.	Influence the integration of telecom innovations with future mobility systems and services.
Recycling & waste management industry	Contribute insights into lifecycle management and environmental sustainability of new mobility systems.	Benefit from inclusion in sustainability frameworks and access to circular economy strategies.
Buildings	Support integration of CCAM into building and urban planning strategies to foster sustainable mobility ecosystems.	Integrate mobility transformation into planning processes and access targeted guidance.
Energy industry	Facilitate the transition to clean energy use within mobility systems, essential for sustainable deployment.	Access models for clean energy adoption in transport and contribute to policy shaping.
People working	Provide firsthand perspectives on training needs and job transition pathways within mobility ecosystems.	Benefit from direct inclusion in training development and tailored support measures.
Unions	Ensure representation and advocacy for fair working conditions and training access across mobility professions.	Engage in shaping fair transition mechanisms and influence social policy outcomes.
Human resources responsables	Offer insights into reskilling practices and workforce evolution within mobility-oriented businesses.	Improve strategic HR practices and access innovative tools for internal workforce transformation.
Unemployed people	Help test and refine inclusion strategies, particularly for vulnerable or transitioning worker groups.	Connect with relevant schemes and policies to support re-entry into emerging job markets.

Stakeholder Sub-Category	Relevance for the Project	Benefits for Stakeholders
International Authorities	Support harmonisation and international relevance of policy approaches developed within RESKILLING.	Benefit from international collaboration, visibility, and exchange of policy innovations.
European Authorities	Help align project outputs with EU policy and legislative frameworks and support dissemination across member states.	Leverage results for implementation across EU frameworks and contribute to policy shaping.
National Authorities	Ensure national-level implementation potential and identify regulatory gaps and opportunities.	Access tailored national-level guidance for CCAM deployment and workforce strategies.
Regional & Local Authorities	Enable localisation and scalability of RESKILLING solutions in diverse territorial contexts.	Apply tested tools to support local employment and skills development efforts.
Enforcement authorities	Provide critical input into legal and safety frameworks for CCAM, ensuring safe and lawful application.	Ensure compliance and contribute to the co-design of enforceable and adaptable legal frameworks.
Funders	Provide mechanisms and perspectives on supporting innovation adoption through financial tools and investment.	Access evidence-based insights and tools to inform investment and funding strategies.
Insurers	Enable analysis of risk management and liability strategies in the context of workforce transition and automation.	Shape how risk is managed in new mobility labour ecosystems and prepare insurance responses.
Transport Infrastructure users /	Represent the everyday users of transport infrastructure and services, whose feedback is vital for assessing the societal impacts of CCAM deployment and shaping user-centric service designs.	Access to better-designed services informed by user needs; participation in pilots and co-creation labs allows influencing future CCAM deployment.
Tourist operators	Play a role in how mobility services support regional and cultural accessibility; their needs reflect seasonal and logistical dimensions of transport planning and skills adaptation.	Opportunity to inform mobility innovation to better serve tourist flows; participation may lead to insights for better seasonal service integration.

3.3. Mapping Method

The stakeholder mapping methodology adopted in RESKILLING is based on a mixed-method approach that combines structured literature review with comparative analysis of stakeholder taxonomies from prior EU-funded projects and institutional frameworks. The objective was not only to replicate existing models, but to critically assess their limitations and expand upon them in ways that reflect RESKILLING’s broader focus on social innovation, inclusion, and labour transitions of CCAM solutions.

The first step involved a targeted analysis of academic publications addressing stakeholder identification and engagement in relation to CCAM, autonomous vehicles, and AI-enabled mobility systems. Among the sources consulted were studies such as [Shibayama et al. \(2019\)](#), [Feys et al. \(2020\)](#), [Atakishiyev et al. \(2021\)](#), [Hamadneh et al. \(2022\)](#), and [Hicks et al. \(2025\)](#). These works provided insight into how stakeholders have been conceptualised, involved, and categorised in earlier research on CCAM governance, deployment, and social acceptance, as well as some other entities

and consulting developing stakeholder maps for different parts of CCAM solutions ([CAV Ireland, 2021](#); [Harbor Research, 2024](#); [Rakhshanfar, P. , 2019](#)).

This academic review was complemented by an in-depth analysis of stakeholder typologies and engagement strategies used in previous and ongoing European initiatives, including the SINFONICA, SHOW, and CCAM ERAS projects, as well as documentation from the CCAM Partnership. These initiatives offered valuable mappings of institutional actors, industry representatives, and user groups relevant to CCAM development and implementation.

However, despite their strengths, a key limitation across these sources was identified: most existing frameworks lacked a holistic dimension to their analysis – an inclusive perspective that considers how roles, vulnerabilities, and agency are distributed across the socio-technical landscape. In particular, they often focused solely on stakeholder roles within the supply chain or policy ecosystem, without accounting for how stakeholder groups are internally structured (e.g. ownership, employment hierarchies, contractual status) or the social positions they occupy (e.g. exposure to job transitions, access to training, influence on decision-making). Such distinctions are essential in the context of CCAM, where automation and connectivity may affect different types of actors in highly differentiated ways, both within and across sectors.

To address this, RESKILLING embedded principles of granularity, differentiation, and functional relevance into its stakeholder taxonomy. One of the decisions was to distinguish between “industry” and “workers” as separate stakeholder groups. This choice reflects the reality that industry actors (such as manufacturers, logistics providers, and platform operators) that related to the CCAM Value Chain and workers (including employees, unions, and the unemployed) refereing to the organisational structure of the stakeholder that can be understodod from different positions in the employment and skills ecosystem and the CCAM one. Drawing from different guidelines from International organisations on pathways for Just Transition ([ILO, 2023](#) ; [UNFCC, 2020](#)), as well as human resource management and labour process theory (Braverman, 1974; Thompson, 1990) and global value chain analysis (Gereffi et al., 2018), his separation allows the project to understand how different categories of stakeholders experience, shape, or are affected by technological transitions — for instance, through upskilling needs, job displacement, or new employment models.

In the same way, the project amplifies its definition of public authorities to include not only transport and urban planners, but also employment agencies, regional development bodies, innovation departments, and other actors who influence how people access jobs, training, and public services related to CCAM. It also incorporated funders and insurers, who play a key role in shaping investment flows, risk allocation, and access to the evolving CCAM economy. This aims to not only reflect sectoral participation, but captures the vertical and horizontal dynamics of influence, vulnerability, and responsibility across the system.

To operationalise this approach, RESKILLING developed a collaborative visual mapping tool using Miro boards, organised into three levels: main stakeholder groups, sub-categories, and stakeholder profiles. This structure allowed for a flexible and iterative refinement of the taxonomy, while supporting alignment with other project components such as training needs assessment and co-creation activities. The visual model (see Figure 2 above) illustrates the main stakeholder groups identified and their interrelations within the CCAM transition.

4. Engagement Activities and Channels

This section details how and where stakeholders will be engaged throughout the duration of RESKILLING and beyond. Engagement is conceived as a cross-cutting and dynamic process that supports the co-creation, validation, and uptake of project results. It is not a standalone task, but rather a core function integrated across multiple work packages, WP3 (Short-, medium- and long-term employment and socio-economic effects of CCAM), WP4 (Towards job creation, growth and innovation), WP5 (Impact Assessment & Roadmap), and WP6 (Communication, dissemination, and exploitation).

The pool of stakeholders identified is defined in RESKILLING as “Stakeholder Community”. This community includes representatives from all the main stakeholder groups identified in the mapping. The community will be mobilised throughout the project, depending on the specific objectives of the activities.

Section 4.1 outlines the types of activities that will be carried out to gather input, co-create knowledge, or test solutions through the different Work Packages and where the stakeholders will be involved. Section 4.2 details strategic collaborations that enhance outreach and alignment with broader initiatives, including the Advisory Board, international cooperation mechanisms, the CCAM Partnership, and other European projects. Sections 4.3 and 4.4 describe the online and offline channels through which these engagements will be organised and maintained. Together, these elements provide a coherent and adaptive framework for stakeholder interaction, ensuring that contributions are timely, relevant, and effectively integrated into RESKILLING’s implementation.

4.1. Planned Co-creation Activities

Stakeholders are engaged across RESKILLING through a variety of targeted activities — including interviews, workshops, consultations, co-creation sessions, and surveys. These activities are designed and implemented within each work package based on its thematic focus and evidence needs, using the Stakeholder Community as a shared pool of actors. Engagement varies in form and intensity depending on the task, but plays a consistent role in informing project outcomes, validating results, and supporting social relevance. Through the communication tools and channels provided by WP6 led by ECTRI, stakeholders are to be involved in the following activities from different Work Packages.

WP2. Stakeholder community engagement

This work package’s objective is to align outreach with a strategic approach for engaging stakeholders and relevant actors affected by, or involved in, the transformation of jobs and skills in the CCAM context.

Task 2.1 – Stakeholder Community Annual events	
Annual events will be organised to convene members of the Stakeholder Community and Advisory Board, ensuring regular exchange, alignment with project milestones, and structured participation in ongoing activities across work packages.	
Activities	To be defined
Lead partner	POLIS
Duration	Month 1 to Month 36

WP3 – Short-, medium- and long-term employment and socio-economic effects of CCAM

This Work Package studies how CCAM technologies are likely to reshape employment across the mobility sector. Stakeholders are involved to assess current and emerging job profiles, co-create knowledge on employment effects, and contribute insights about vulnerable workforce group.

Task 3.1 – Professions and Jobs in the CCAM Value Chain

During M1–M12, stakeholders from all groups and Advisory Board members are consulted to assess job transformations across the CCAM value chain.

Activities	Stakeholder consultations
Lead partner	Zaragoza Logistics Center
Duration	Month 1 to Month 12

Task 3.2 - Employment Effects of CCAM and co-creation workshops

A broad engagement effort conducted between M3–M18 includes over 50 interviews with stakeholders from various sectors, and two co-creation workshops held in M9 and M17, bringing together at least 20 experts.

Activities	Stakeholder consultations ; Interviews
Lead partner	ECORYS
Duration	Month 9 and 17; and Month 3 to 18

Task 3.3 – Effects on Special Workforce Groups

This task involves more than 20 interviews with job providers and over 20 additional interviews with representatives of vulnerable groups, complemented by a dedicated workshop on month 17.

Activities	Stakeholder consultations; Interviews
Lead partner	CERTH; ECORYS
Duration	Month 3 to 18; Month 17

Task 3.4 – Short, Medium, and Long-Term Socioeconomic Effects

Stakeholder involvement is foreseen throughout the task (M12–M30) depending on the design of the socioeconomic impact framework.

Activities	Cost-benefit analysis (CBA), focus groups, and surveys
Lead partner	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Duration	Month 12 to 30

Task 3.5 – RESKILLING Use Cases

Stakeholders, including affected workers and users, may be involved in specific use cases (M12–M18) based on the implementation context.

Activities	Case-specific stakeholder involvement
Lead partner	CERTH
Duration	Month 12 to 18

WP4 - Towards job creation, growth and innovation

WP4 is centered on facilitating businesses and workers to respond to the challenges and opportunities presented by the deployment of CCAM through the following means: business model innovation, (re)skilling, and the provision of support for sustainable employment. Stakeholders are engaged to help identify skills needs, co-develop training pathways, validate tools, and contribute to social innovation processes that enhance job retention and inclusive growth.

Task 4.1 – Business models & schemes for CCAM innovation and jobs promotion

Stakeholder interviews with industry actors (at least 60) are being conducted. A landmark event will take place within this task, with the Business model Camp Stakeholder workshop will also be held with 30 external stakeholders.

Activities	Interviews; BM Camp workshop
Lead partner	BAX
Duration	Month 12 to 32

Task 4.2 - Horizontal Social Innovation Network

A series of interviews and labs will engage stakeholders across the quadruple helix regarding good practices for social innovation in M15, M21, and M27 to build a Social Innovation Network.

Activities	Interviews, co-creation labs
Lead partner	VDI/VDE-IT
Duration	Month 9 to 27; Month 15, 21, 27

Task 4.3 – Re-training Schemes Prioritisation through AHP

Selected stakeholders will participate in a survey-based prioritisation of re-training schemes using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology.

Activities	Prioritisation survey
Lead partner	Zaragoza Logistics Center
Duration	Month 10 to 13

Task 4.5 – CCAM Employment & Skills Observatory

This online Observatory will offer targeted, user-driven insights into jobs, skills, and emerging roles affected by CCAM deployment. Stakeholders will contribute through feedback loops and tailored engagement based on their profiles.

Activities	Feedback collection
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Lead partner	CERTH
Duration	Month 6 to 36

Task 4.6 – Multi-layered Replication and Transferability

Stakeholder engagement with actors from rail, maritime, aviation, and CCAM domains is planned to validate the transferability potential of RESKILLING outputs.

Activities	To be defined
Lead partner	EURNEX
Duration	Month 24 to 32

WP5 - Impact Assessment & Roadmap

Work Package 5 is responsible for the assessment of the socioeconomic and employment impacts of CCAM, in addition to the development of policy recommendations and a roadmap for an inclusive transition.

Task 5.1 – Impact Assessment

Stakeholders are invited to provide feedback support indicator development, contribute to validation, and ensure alignment with policy and regulatory shifts through a dedicated legislative foresight team.

Activities	To be defined
Lead partner	Research Centre for Transport and Logistics (CTL)
Duration	Month 1 to 36

Task 5.3 – Guidelines and Policy Recommendations

Stakeholders will be consulted to ensure that policy messages and recommendations are grounded in practice and reflect social, territorial and industrial needs. This will occur between M24 and M32 and will be developed in coordination with the Stakeholder Community.

Activities	To be defined
Lead partner	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Duration	Month 24 to 32

Task 5.4 – Roadmap to support the socio-economic transition to CCAM

Stakeholders will be consulted to ensure that the RESKILLING Roadmap is aligned with stakeholder expectations, industry needs, and regulatory frameworks. This will occur between M24 and M35 and will be developed in coordination with the Stakeholder Community.

Activities	To be defined
Lead partner	CERTH
Duration	Month 24 to 36

WP6 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation

This work package is in charge of ensuring that the activities and results of RESKILLING are both widely visible and readily adopted by relevant parties through a comprehensive communications and dissemination strategy. It provides the tools and channels for stakeholder engagement and facilitate interaction between the consortium and external audiences, including the website, repository, social media, and public events, among others.

Task 6.2 – Final Conference	
The Final Conference will bring together stakeholders from across the project to discuss results, lessons learned, and future directions on CCAM solutions going beyond RESKILLING.	
Activities	Conference
Lead partner	ECTRI
Duration	Month 35

4.2. Strategic Collaborations

RESKILLING’s engagement strategy is reinforced by a series of targeted collaborations that support the project’s scientific, institutional, and international ambitions. These collaborations serve to expand the reach and credibility of the project, ensure alignment with ongoing research and policy agendas, and introduce external perspectives into the design and validation of its outputs. Three key areas of structured collaboration have been established: the Advisory Board, international cooperation, and liaison with the CCAM Partnership and relevant projects.

Advisory Board

The Advisory Board (AB) of RESKILLING is an independent, non-decision-making body that serves as a strategic and multidisciplinary body designed to enhance the project’s quality, relevance, and alignment with broader CCAM, labour transformation, and social innovation agendas. It was formally established by Month 5 (May 2025) and will operate until the project’s conclusion in December 2027. It is composed of 11 members from European and non-European countries: Belgium, Spain, UK, Germany, The Netherlands, Norway, Italy, France, Greece, and the United States.

The AB is conceived as an active, structured mechanism for external review, expert consultation, and foresight. Its mandate includes guiding the project on emerging trends, ethical considerations, and alignment with international research and policy developments. It brings together recognised professionals from:

- CCAM and transport innovation fields;
- Labour unions and industrial associations;
- Social sciences and academia;
- Organisations specialising in social innovation and employment policy.

The AB is coordinated and chaired by the International Road Federation (IRF), which also acts as the liaison between the Advisory Board and the Project Management Team. IRF is responsible for (a) organising and convening annual AB meetings; (b) managing written consultations on strategic

issues; (c) coordinating the external review of selected deliverables (in collaboration with the project's Quality Manager) and; (d) consolidating feedback and ensuring its integration into project decisions and outcomes.

The AB will meet three times over the course of the project: once during the first year, once at the mid-point, and once at the final event. Between these meetings, members may also be invited to:

- Provide written feedback on high-priority deliverables such as use cases, employment and socioeconomic impact assessments, training schemes, and the final roadmap;
- Participate in stakeholder events, expert panels, or co-creation workshops;
- Respond to ad-hoc requests from the Management team in case of unforeseen challenges or strategic questions.

Feedback from the AB will be consolidated and formally incorporated into the internal quality assurance process for key deliverables. In addition to reviewing technical soundness and innovation, AB members are asked to assess clarity, usability, and policy relevance of RESKILLING outputs.

The Advisory Board also plays an important role in supporting international cooperation, acting as a bridge between the project and expert communities outside the EU. Through their networks and contributions, AB members will help ensure that RESKILLING reflects global insights, remains at the forefront of research and practice, and contributes to shaping future directions in inclusive CCAM deployment.

International Cooperation

RESKILLING incorporates international cooperation as a core element of its outreach and impact strategy. Through dedicated partners such as IRF, FEHRL, UITP, and ECTRI, the project builds on existing relationships with a wide range of R&D centres, transport authorities, and policy platforms across Europe and globally.

Initial cooperation has been established with:

- US Transportation Research Board (TRB);
- International Transport Forum (ITF);
- International Labour Organisation (ILO);
- PIARC (World Road Association);
- UIC (International Union of Railways).

In addition, RESKILLING benefits from established links with transport research organisations in South Africa (CSIR), Japan (PWRI), South Korea (KOTI), and China (CHTS), as well as evolving collaboration with stakeholders in Singapore and Australia. These relationships support knowledge exchange on CCAM deployment, labour policy, and inclusive innovation practices.

To facilitate continuous collaboration, the project will host annual virtual concertation events, each involving representatives from at least four non-EU countries. These will focus on dialogue around labour transitions, CCAM innovation, and governance strategies, particularly with experts combining technical and social science expertise.

CCAM Partnership and Related Projects

RESKILLING maintains a structured liaison with the **CCAM Partnership**, particularly through active involvement of its partners in **Cluster 6: Societal Aspects and People Needs**. The project contributes to the ongoing development of the CCAM Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), the Code of Conduct, and knowledge-sharing mechanisms.

Specific activities include:

- Identifying areas of alignment with the CCAM Partnership's KPI framework and strategic priorities;
- Sharing results, tools, and insights from RESKILLING with CCAM clusters and working groups;
- Incorporating stakeholder engagement activities into the broader CCAM user and innovation ecosystem.

Additionally, liaison activities extend to relevant current projects, indicatively including:

- **CCAM-ERAS**, on the socio-economic transition to CCAM;
- **CCAmbassador**, on the coordination and alignment efforts of the CCAM Partnership by expanding stakeholder engagement beyond research, innovation and experts' communities;
- **CulturalRoad**, on new guidelines for the effective and equitable deployment of CCAM services, taking into account cultural and geographical diversity;
- **Diversify-CCAM**, on integrating social diversities in the design and implementation of CCAM across all European landscapes;
- **ULTIMO**, on creating economically feasible and sustainable integration of AVs for MaaS public transportation and LaaS urban goods transportation.

Engagement with the CCAM Partnership is structured around three main collaboration channels:

1. Internal contribution to strategic priorities

RESKILLING benefits from the direct involvement of several partners in the CCAM Partnership, with VTI acting as co-leader of Cluster 6: Societal Aspects and People Needs, and Dr. Evangelos Bekiaris (CERTH) being member of the CCAM Partnership Board, representing the Research Bodies. The connection enables the consortium to stay informed about evolving priorities and ensure that RESKILLING's internal activities remain coherent with ongoing efforts in the cluster. Contributions will take the form of shared insights, targeted feedback, and structured exchanges where appropriate.

2. Bilateral coordination with ongoing projects

RESKILLING will establish bilateral exchanges with relevant European projects under the CCAM umbrella, such as the previously mentioned projects (non-exhaustive list). These interactions will aim to identify shared interests and exchange approaches to common challenges (e.g. business model development, training design, or data governance). Opportunities to coordinate stakeholder engagement efforts and to pool stakeholder communities will also be explored to avoid duplication and maximise reach.

3. Dissemination through CCAM Partnership channels

RESKILLING will use both internal and external communication tools of the CCAM Partnership to increase visibility of its work. This includes contributing to Cluster 6 exchanges, sharing updates via internal newsletters or mailing lists, and leveraging external-facing CCAM platforms and social media to promote RESKILLING events, findings, and stakeholder opportunities.

4.3. Online Engagement Channels

To ensure broad, sustained and effective engagement, RESKILLING is deploying a set of online channels that serve communication, knowledge diffusion, stakeholder interaction and long-term accessibility purposes. These tools have been developed and are being maintained in coordination with Work Package 6 lead, ECTRI – and are supported by a commitment to Open Science and project identity. All visual materials, user interfaces and downloadable content will follow the RESKILLING visual identity, ensuring consistency and recognisability across formats and platforms.

Project Website

The RESKILLING website acts as the main access point for all project-related public information. This website is already available at <https://reskilling-project.eu/>. A dedicated Stakeholder Section will:

- Detail engagement opportunities (e.g. events, surveys, co-creation labs);
- Outline the benefits of participation, including early access to research insights and co-creation opportunities;
- Offer a registration form for individuals and organisations wishing to join the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community;

The website and its materials will remain publicly accessible for at least three years after the project's conclusion, to ensure sustained knowledge access and policy use.

Mailing List and Newsletters

Stakeholders registered through the website will be invited to subscribe to the RESKILLING newsletters, which will be used to:

- Send targeted event invitations and opportunities to contribute;
- Share thematic project updates in the form of two newsletters per year;
- Disseminate open access content, press releases, and summaries of key milestones.

Social Media

RESKILLING will use targeted social media channels to increase visibility, promote results, and enable light-touch interaction with stakeholders and the wider public. These activities will be closely coordinated by WP6 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, led by ECTRI) to ensure strategic alignment across platforms.

Key actions include:

- LinkedIn project page: A public-facing page will be created and actively managed to share major milestones, call-outs for stakeholder involvement, publication announcements, and video content. The page will also help build professional credibility around RESKILLING's outcomes and facilitate network expansion.
- YouTube channel: This channel will contain RESKILLING promotional videos as well as the different webinars organised around the topic.

Stakeholder Forum

To complement structured engagement tools such as the website, mailing list, and CCAM Employment & Skills Observatory, RESKILLING will establish an interactive Stakeholder Forum — a private online platform designed to host and support ongoing dialogue, collaboration, and knowledge exchange among members of the RESKILLING Stakeholder Community.

The Forum will provide a **dedicated digital space** for stakeholders to:

- Access tailored information and updates based on their sector, role, or area of interest (e.g. training providers, social partners, mobility operators);
- Engage in peer-to-peer dialogue, exchanging challenges, solutions, and practices related to the CCAM transition and labour transformation;
- Receive invitations to contribute to co-creation activities, workshops, surveys, and testing exercises relevant to their expertise or geographical context;
- Explore project materials, ask questions to the RESKILLING team, and follow topic-specific threads related to WP3, WP4, and WP5 outputs;
- Join targeted sub-groups for specific themes (e.g. youth employment, rural mobility, human resources innovation), supporting cross-sectoral learning and network building.

This Forum will be set up independently from the website and managed by POLIS, but linked on the RESKILLING website in the Stakeholder Forum part. Quotes have been investigated at the stage of submission of this plan, and the platform developer will be selected during the summer, to set up the Forum in September 2025 (M9).

4.4. Offline Engagement Channels

RESKILLING combines online and offline activities to ensure broad, inclusive, and sustained stakeholder participation. Offline channels play a critical role in building trust, enabling deliberation, and strengthening visibility among diverse audiences. These include project-organised workshops, participation in major European and international events, and the strategic use of communication materials for face-to-face engagement.

Events and Meetings

RESKILLING will participate in and organise a variety of in-person events in order to generate engagement from stakeholders.

- Project-organised workshops and co-creation sessions: These will be embedded in relevant phases of the project and are designed to gather input on emerging findings, validate tools,

and support policy recommendations. In-person formats will be prioritised where possible to support mutual learning and trust building. These meetings will support the addition of new stakeholders through their promotion on the projects and partners

- Third-party events: RESKILLING partners will participate in European and international conferences such as TRA, TRB, ITS World/Europe, UITP Summit, POLIS Conference, CIVITAS Forum, TEN-T Days, ECER conference and the Smart City Expo World Congress, among others. Participation in these fora will support both dissemination and stakeholder recruitment, and help connect RESKILLING with linked projects and initiatives. Events may also host RESKILLING workshops and public sessions, creating synergies between research, stakeholder dialogue, and policy outreach.

Physical Communication Materials

These materials based on RESKILLING visual identify are designed not only for awareness raising but also for supporting deeper understanding and capacity building. These will include:

- Brochures, leaflets, and banners;
- Roll-ups and posters;
- Policy summaries and deliverable highlights distributed at stakeholder events.

5. Timeline

This section provides an overview of the stakeholder engagement activities scheduled across the duration of the RESKILLING project. These activities are tightly integrated with the project's research, co-creation, and dissemination processes and are designed to ensure meaningful, timely, and coordinated involvement of key stakeholder groups. This timeline reflects the current plan as of Month 12 (M12) and will be formally updated at M18 and again at M28 to ensure alignment with project developments.

Stakeholders are engaged through workshops, interviews, surveys, labs, expert panels, and virtual events, involving actors across the CCAM value chain. The planning and implementation of these engagements are managed by the responsible WP or Task leader in coordination with POLIS (WP2), who holds overall responsibility for stakeholder engagement coherence and tracking.

- **Coordination Mechanism**

To ensure consistency and quality in stakeholder interactions, all partners leading engagement activities must:

- Notify POLIS at least four weeks in advance of any planned stakeholder engagement activity (e.g., workshop, survey, interviews, event).
- Share key details of the engagement, including purpose, target groups, formats, and any materials requiring stakeholder input.
- Coordinate with POLIS to:
 - Cross-reference the stakeholder repository and identify suitable profiles or contacts.
 - Ensure GDPR compliance and coherence with the engagement methodology.
 - Log the activity in the Engagement Tracking Tool (ETT) for internal reporting.
- Brief POLIS on planned follow-up activities and stakeholder feedback mechanisms.

This mechanism ensures stakeholder fatigue is minimised, outreach is coordinated, and insights can be systematically captured and shared across the Consortium.

- Year 1 (M1–M12)
 - M3–M6: Development of the stakeholder engagement methodology and first version of the stakeholder repository (T2.2).
 - M4: Establishment of the Advisory Board and definition of its operational framework (T2.4).
 - M6: Submission of Deliverables D2.1 (Engagement Methodology) and D2.2 (Stakeholder Community Report).
 - M3–M12: Stakeholder mapping and first wave of interviews for WP3 (T3.1–T3.3), engaging at least two representatives per group.
 - M9: First co-creation workshop on CCAM employment effects (WP3 – ECORYS).
 - M10–M13: AHP-based survey involving selected stakeholders for re-training prioritisation (WP4 – ZLC).

- M12: First Stakeholder Engagement Event (virtual), showcasing early findings and gathering feedback.
- Year 2 (M13–M24)
 - M15: First co-creation lab on business models and social innovation (WP4 – VDI/VDE-IT).
 - M17: Second co-creation workshop on employment effects (WP3 – ECORYS).
 - M18: Submission of D4.6 (CCAM Employment & Skills Observatory), integrating stakeholder inputs and ETT data.
 - M18: Update of D2.2, refining engagement plans based on results.
 - M21: Second co-creation lab (WP4 – VDI/VDE-IT).
 - M24: Second Advisory Board meeting to review mid-term progress.
- Year 3 (M25–M36)
 - M27: Third co-creation lab (WP4 – VDI/VDE-IT).
 - M28: Second Stakeholder Engagement Event (virtual), testing replication approaches and draft recommendations.
 - M30–M32: Stakeholder consultations for assessing toolkit transferability (WP4 – EURNEX).
 - M32–M34: Consultations for policy guidelines and roadmap development (WP5 – VUB).
 - M35: Final conference (WP6 – ECTRI) with high-level stakeholder participation.
 - M36: Final Advisory Board meeting and consolidated reporting of stakeholder engagement (T2.3).

This timeline ensures that stakeholder engagement is embedded across all phases of RESKILLING and remains coherent, targeted, and inclusive. Each engagement moment contributes to both project outputs and community-building efforts, with the Engagement Tracking Tool (ETT) and Repository supporting traceability, analysis, and follow-up. A visual timeline has been prepared and shared with partners to ensure alignment. It is available in annex (See part 9. Annexes).

7. Next steps

7.1. Implementation and Update

The methodology described in the deliverable will be implemented in a coordinated manner between all RESKILLING partners, under the lead of POLIS.

Deliverable 2.3 will include a version of the two tools mentioned, which will be populated from the moment project activities engaging stakeholders start.

In addition to a free access to the tracking tools, WP2 monthly calls will be used to review the update of the tools and deliverables 2.1 and 2.3.

7.2. Risk Management

This section identifies and anticipates the main risks associated with stakeholder engagement in the RESKILLING project. As this deliverable lays the foundation for all related activities (mapping, engagement, observatory, outreach), it must also foresee potential vulnerabilities and define appropriate mitigation strategies. Several of these risks were highlighted in the Grant Agreement, while others emerge from the complexity of engaging a wide and diverse stakeholder community. The following risks are therefore monitored throughout the project lifecycle and addressed through specific mechanisms, tools, and procedures.

Risk 1. Low participation from key stakeholders groups (e.g. labour unions, users, social partners)

There is a possibility that certain stakeholder categories—despite being strategically relevant—may deprioritise engagement due to limited resources, lack of alignment, or competing agendas

Mitigation:

A structured coordination mechanism is in place whereby WP leads must notify POLIS, as engagement coordinator, prior to stakeholder outreach. This allows targeted support and matchmaking via the Stakeholder Repository, which stores relevant profiles, past interactions, and engagement preferences. Where gaps are detected, POLIS can initiate targeted re-engagement campaigns (e.g. direct emails, follow-up calls, additional rounds of invitations). The repository also helps track balance between categories, ensuring proportional representation.

Risk 2. Insufficient involvement from industry stakeholders (e.g. SMEs, service providers, OEMs, energy/telecom actors)

Private sector actors may perceive engagement activities as having low immediate relevance or unclear benefit.

Mitigation:

Industry stakeholders are primarily engaged through WP4 (Business Models & Innovation Toolkit), where their input feeds directly into economically viable outputs. Use cases, co-creation labs, and interviews are framed around business value, workforce planning, and innovation needs. Furthermore, industry actors will be involved in the Advisory Board and the CCAM Employment &

Skills Observatory design, offering tailored spaces for influence. For example, training curricula and skills forecasting will be explicitly aligned with HR and reskilling needs emerging from these sectors.

Risk 3. Limited gender balance and inclusion across engagement activities

Stakeholder engagement may risk reproducing existing gender or representation imbalances in the transport and mobility sector.

Mitigation:

WP2 and WP6 will apply gender-sensitive design principles, including in the formulation of invitations, event panels, and interview sampling. The Stakeholder Repository will allow monitoring gender-disaggregated participation, and gaps will be addressed by engaging women-led networks or underrepresented actors. Specific attention will be given to including perspectives of those impacted by automation, including through T3.3 (special workforce groups).

Risk 4. Stakeholder fatigue or one-time participation

Stakeholders may contribute once (e.g. via interview or workshop), but not remain active throughout the project lifecycle.

Mitigation:

The Stakeholder Forum offers a persistent and evolving digital space for continued interaction. Stakeholders will be onboarded after every major activity (e.g. workshops, surveys) and invited to follow targeted discussion threads by category or interest. The Engagement Tracking Tool (ETT) will identify inactive or low-return participants and prompt specific re-engagement actions, supported by WP leads and WP6.

Risk 5. Low uptake of the online Stakeholder Forum

Despite being designed as a key engagement tool, the Forum may suffer from limited use if not clearly structured or promoted.

Mitigation:

Forum content will be curated by POLIS and WP lead partners to align with stakeholder profiles: announcements, thematic spaces, and Q&As will reflect real-time project activities and stakeholder concerns. The Forum will also be used to disseminate updates tied to stakeholder roles (e.g. job taxonomy, curricula, roadmap). To ensure uptake, all stakeholders engaged offline will receive personalised invitations and be offered onboarding support. A pop-up registration widget will also be integrated into the website and newsletter. A review of the stakeholder platform analytics will take place every month with WP2 partners to diagnose the integration of stakeholders into the platform with the subsequent measures to act in case of negative feedback.

Risk 6. Conflicting views among stakeholder categories that impact consensus

Given the diversity of actors—from regulators to industry and civil society—conflicting expectations may challenge co-design outputs.

Mitigation:

Participatory methods and moderation techniques will be in place used to surface tensions early and channel them constructively. Validation stages are embedded in WP5 deliverables to ensure all stakeholder types can review outputs before finalisation. Where divergence occurs, WP leads will transparently document different positions and propose compromise scenarios in the policy recommendations or roadmap. The Stakeholder Platform will also provide with some community guidelines and will establish mechanisms to avoid any conflict between platform users and/or partners.

**Risk 7. Low participation in Stakeholder Community
online registration and events**

Stakeholders may not proactively register in the interactive forms used to build the community database, limiting reach.

Mitigation:

POLIS will align with Communication lead ECTRI, as well as the lead partner of activities to create targeted campaigns and event registration flows to promote registration. The website's stakeholder section will clearly explain benefits and offer short-form, interest-based registration (linked to the Stakeholder Repository). Onsite workshop participants will be invited to register during or immediately after the event to avoid loss of contact. Specific targets are set to track progress.

Risk 8. Uneven coverage of stakeholder groups or underrepresentation of key geographies

Despite efforts to map and include a broad pool of stakeholders, some regions or sub-groups may remain underrepresented.

Mitigation:

The Repository includes geographical markers and will be reviewed biannually to identify coverage gaps. Partners from underrepresented regions will be encouraged to nominate candidates or institutions for involvement, as well as an active effort will be taken from POLIS together with Communication Lead ECTRI. The Advisory Board also includes members from diverse contexts, and their networks will be leveraged to improve regional balance.

8. Conclusions

The deliverable 2.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan guides all activities involving external stakeholders in the RESKILLING project. These activities affect the work in all WPs, and will have a great impact on the project results' quality. Therefore, the structure, clarity and exhaustivity of this deliverable are key for the succes of the project.

In parallel, this plan relies on several other actions in WP6 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation), such as the set up of the project website, social media, and the definition of processes for promotional events, etc. It also supports WP6 by providing target audiences for the RESKILLING key messages and setting up communication channels and monitoring tools with external stakeholders. This strong connection with WP6 is crucial for the implementation of this deliverable.

Finally, all activities planned and described in this deliverable will be reported upon in the deliverable 2.3 Stakeholder Engagement Report. These two deliverables should be considered together, and will also be regularly updated in common periods. D2.3 defines Key Performance Indicators to ensure the completion of targets and objectives set up in D2.1.

To conclude, all partners are invited to participate in the implementation of this plan, and have been consulted in its development through different stages. The guidelines described will be adapted in the course of the project depending on contexts and results, so internal communication and collaboration will be the main condition ensuring its success.

9. References

- Bozzini, A., & Pascual Dapena, M. (2025). *Towards meaningful civil society participation at the international level: Success factors, opportunities and challenges*. OECD Working Papers on Public Governance, No. 81. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/8ed04dc2-en>
- Braverman, H. (1998). *Labor and monopoly capital: The degradation of work in the twentieth century*. NYU Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt9qfrkf>
- Bryson, J. M., Quick, K. S., Slotterback, C. S., & Crosby, B. C. (2013). Designing public participation processes. *Public Administration Review*, 73(1), 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2012.02678.x>
- CAV Ireland. (2021). *Data and the future of autonomous vehicles*. <https://www.cavireland.com/data-and-the-future-of-autonomous-vehicles/>
- Durham, E., Baker, H., Smith, M., Moore, E., & Morgan, V. (2014). *The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook*. BiodivERsA.
- Feys, M., Rombaut, E., Macharis, C., & Vanhaverbeke, L. (2020). Understanding stakeholders' evaluation of autonomous vehicle services complementing public transport in an urban context. In *2020 Forum on Integrated and Sustainable Transportation Systems (FISTS)* (pp. 341–346). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FISTS46898.2020.9264856>
- Gereffi, G., Fernandez-Stark, K., & Gereffi, G. (2018). Global value chain analysis: A primer (Second edition). In *Global value chains and development: Redefining the contours of 21st century capitalism* (pp. 305–342). Cambridge University Press.
- Hamadneh, J., Duleba, S., & Esztergár-Kiss, D. (2022). Stakeholder viewpoints analysis of the autonomous vehicle industry by using multi-actors multi-criteria analysis. *Transport Policy*, 126, 65–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2022.07.005>
- Harbor Research. (2024). *Chaos, collaboration and connected cars*. <https://harborresearch.com/chaos-collaboration-connected-cars/#download>
- Hicks, D., Isett, K. R., & Kingsley, G. (2025). Steering the future: Expert knowledge and stakeholder voices in autonomous vehicle policy reports. *Policy and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/polsoc/puae041>
- Hollebeek, L. D., Urbonavicius, S., Sigurdsson, V., & Clark, M. (2022). Stakeholder engagement and business model innovation value. *The Service Industries Journal*, 42(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2022.2026334>
- International Labour Organization. (2023). *The role of active labour market policies for a just transition*. <https://doi.org/10.54394/VOWE8267>
- Kochskämper, E., Challies, E., Jager, N. W., & Newig, J. (Eds.). (2017). *Participation for effective environmental governance: Evidence from European Water Framework Directive implementation* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315193649>

- Kujala, J., Sachs, S., Leinonen, H., Heikkinen, A., & Laude, D. (2022). Stakeholder engagement: Past, present, and future. *Business & Society*, 61(5), 1136–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503211066595>
- OECD. (2024). Stakeholder engagement and collaboration in STI for the green transition. *OECD Policy Briefs, No. 9*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/80de5e48-en>
- Oliveira, R. R., Fernandes, G., & Pardini, D. J. (2023). Stakeholder engagement as a determinant of the governance in projects. *Procedia Computer Science*, 217, 3732–3741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.01.448>
- Phillips, W., Lee, H., Ghobadian, A., O'Regan, N., & James, P. (2015). Social innovation and social entrepreneurship: A systematic review. *Group & Organization Management*, 40(3), 428–461. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601114560063>
- Rakhshanfar, P. (2019). AV value chain — Data perspective. *Medium*. <https://medium.com/caliber-data-labs/av-value-chain-data-perspective-c50d5abd98ea>
- Reed, M. S., Vella, S., Challies, E., de Vente, J., Frewer, L., Hohenwallner-Ries, D., Huber, T., Neumann, R. K., Oughton, E. A., Sidoli del Ceno, J., & van Delden, H. (2018). A theory of participation: What makes stakeholder and public engagement in environmental management work? *Restoration Ecology*, 26(S1), S7–S17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.12541>
- Reznikova, L., Labanino, R., & McKee Mathews, D. (2024). Pooling our strengths: The power of stakeholder engagement in education and skills policy. *OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers, No. 316*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/b73697cb-en>
- Shibayama, T., Pungillo, G., Lemmerer, H., & Nocera, S. (2020). Stakeholder involvement in decision-making process: A test assessment towards transition to autonomous vehicles. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 48, 2550–2568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.08.255>
- Thompson, P. (1990). Crawling from the wreckage. In D. Knights & H. Willmott (Eds.), *Labour process theory*. MacMillan.

Additional

file:

Sinfonica Project. (2023). *CCAM vocabulary and stakeholders' needs and requirements for CCAM solutions*. <https://sinfonica.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/D1.2-CCAM-vocabulary-and-stakeholders-needs-and-requirements-for-CCAM-solutions.pdf>

Research initiative for Enhancing and Adapting Workforce SKILLS for Implementing TraNsport

10. Annexes

Research initiative for Enhancing and Adapting Workforce SKILLS for Implementing Transport Automation with Employment Growth

10.1. Annex 1: Stakeholder Map

10.2.2. Annex 2.2: Engagement Timeline by Stakeholder Category

Stakeholder Types	Stakeholder Sub-Types	Stakeholder Categories	Stakeholder Sub-Categories	Stakeholder examples	Involved stakeholders	Active stakeholders	Relevance	Benefits	Timeline		
Transport operators	Service providers	Passenger transport service providers					Provide real-world use cases, user feedback, and infrastructure access for deployment and piloting of tools.	Gain early access to tools and strategies that enhance operational models and service delivery.	M1-12 interviews for T3.1 M3-18 Interviews for T3.2 M9 & M17 workshops for T3.2 M3-18 Interviews for T3.3 & T3.4 M12-18 Support Use case definition for T3.5 M9-15 Interviews for T4.2 M15, 21, 27 Labs for T4.2 M24-32 feedback on recommendations for T5.3		
		Logistics service providers									
		Fleet owners									
		Fleet operators									
		On demand transport operators									
		Car-sharing platform operators									
	Military transport service providers										
	Technology providers	Digital innovators/developers	ITS associations					Enable the technological integration and application of RESKILLING tools through innovation and product alignment.		Align product offerings with cutting-edge CCAM workforce and policy strategies.	
			Telecom operators	System designers							
				Data management	Data collection						
				AI researchers	Data storage						
	MaaS service providers	Software developers	Data labeling								
Infrastructure operators	Road/Railways owners						Support the adaptation and testing of infrastructure to meet new mobility demands.	Shape the adaptation of infrastructure to emerging technological and social demands.			
	Road/railway operators										
	Ports/Airports/Train & Coach stations/Parking operators										
Industry	Transport industry	Vehicle manufacturers	Vehicle designers								
			Factories								
			Pre-delivery inspection & storage parking lots								
		Vehicle components manufacturers									
		Signalling manufacturers									
		Repair & Maintenance operators	Workshops								
	Repair centers										
	Bodyshops										
	Recycling & waste management industry	Assistance & tow trucks									
		Fast fitters									
	Energy industry	Energy providers									
		Grid owners									
	Buildings	Architects									
		Construction industry									
Telecom industry	Real Estate										
	Device Manufacturers										
	Device Maintenance										
	Equipment Providers										
	Infrastructure Installers										
	Infrastructure Maintenance										

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Stakeholder Types	Stakeholder Sub-Types	Stakeholder Categories	Stakeholder Sub-Categories	Stakeholder examples	Involved stakeholders	Active stakeholders	Relevance	Benefits	Timeline	
Workers	Unions	Unions' associations							M1-12 Interviews for T3.1 M3-18 Interviews for T3.2 M9 & M17 workshops for T3.2 M3-18 Interviews for T3.3 & T3.4 M12-18 Support Use case definition for T3.5 M9-15 Interviews for T4.2 M15, 21, 27 Labs for T4.2 M24-32 feedback on recommendations for T5.3	
		National unions								
		Local unions								
	HR responsables								Same as above + M6-32 Interviews for T4.1	
	People working	Operational workers	Service Workers		Drivers (Emergency, Goods, Passengers)					M1-12 interviews for T3.1 M9 & M17 workshops for T3.2 M3-18 Interviews for T3.2 M3-18 Interviews for T3.3 & T3.4 M9-15 Interviews for T4.2 M15, 21, 27 Labs for T4.2
					Ticket sellers					
					Ticket controllers					
			Industry workers		Police & Enforcement workers					
				Vehicle jockeys						
					Designers					
				Safety controllers						
			Factory workers							
	Other operational workers		Repair & Maintenance workers							
	Instructors									
	Planners		Traffic managers							
	Service intermediaries		Transport system planners							
			Booking hotlines							
			Booking apps/platforms							
	Innovation workers		Cybersecurity workers							
	Unemployed	Potential Workers								
Authorities	International authorities						Standards & policies influencing CCAM deployment	Insights from global best practices	M1-12 interviews for T3.1 M9 & M17 workshops for T3.2 M9-15 Interviews for T4.2 M15, 21, 27 Labs for T4.2	
	European authorities						Regulatory framework & funding for CCAM deployment	Harmonisation across sites/MIS; Stakeholder cooperation facilitation		
	National authorities	Economic development & innovation Ministry Labour Ministry Transport Ministry Defense Ministry						National regulatory frameworks & testing facilities impact CCAM deployment	Ensure safety & adaptation to national regulations; Enhance national trainings with field data	M24-32 feedback on recommendations for T5.3
	Local & regional authorities	Transportation planners						CCAM integration into local environments & transport systems	Ensure alignment of CCAM deployment with local policy objectives; Local workforce & skills development	Same as above + M3-18 Interviews for T3.3 & T3.4 M12-18 Support Use case definition for T3.5
		City planners								
	Employment Agencies									
	Enforcement Authorities									
	Standard definition organisations									

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Stakeholder Types	Stakeholder Sub-Types	Stakeholder Categories	Stakeholder Sub-Categories	Stakeholder examples	Involved stakeholders	Active stakeholders	Relevance	Benefits	Timeline
Funders & Insurers	Funders	Private funders	Private banks Charities						
		Public funders	Subsidy managers Public banks						
	Insurers	Call centers & hotlines							
		Reinsurers assessing risks							
Researchers & Educators	Universities	University direction/Programme designers & deciders							
		Professors							
		Students							
	Researchers	Economists							
		Social scientists							
		Transport innovators							
	Vocational/Technical training institutions	Environment researchers							
		Occupational standardisation bodies							
		Professional trainers							
		Teachers							
Life-long learning organisations	Private Research Centers / Institutes								
	Innovation Clusters								
End-users	Transport / Infrastructure users	Car drivers							
		Passengers							
		Cyclists							
		Pedestrians							
	Tourist operators								
		Event organisers							
	Consumers	Services of General interest	Schools						
		Healthcare							
		Individual Consumers	Car drivers / Buyers						
	Organised civil society	E-commerce buyers							
		Businesses	Logistics buyers						
		Special workforce / User groups							
		Neighbourhood management							
		Carpooling networks/Ride on bench							
Age groups									
Sensory or physical disabilities groups									
Minority representation	Gender groups								
Ethnic minorities									
Economic minorities									
Associations (e.g., Drivers, Cyclists, etc.)									

M1-12 Interviews for T3.1
M9 & M17 workshops for T3.2
M3-18 Interviews for T3.2
M3-18 Interviews for T3.3 & T3.4